

High-Speed Energy-Efficient Signed Multiplier For FPGA Based Hardware Accelerators

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Abstract:

In modern digital system architectures, multiplication is essential for performing computational tasks such as convolution operations, which are extensively utilized in applications related to digital signal processing (DSP). These operations require signed multipliers that are both high-speed and energy-efficient to fulfill the requirements of performance-critical applications. Multiplication is inherently resource-intensive and has a considerable effect on speed and performance of processors, making the design of fast and efficient multiplication units essential. This work focuses on designing multiplier that operates at a high-speed and consumes less power. The implementation and design of the multipliers with lesser delay and power supports rapid prototyping and customization, making them ideal for FPGA based real-time processing applications.

Keywords: Signed fixed-point multiplier, Booth radix-16, high speed, field-programmable gate array, pipeline registers

Introduction

The multiplier is an essential element in digital signal processing (DSP), hardware accelerator applications, designed to efficiently handle arithmetic operations involving signed fixed-point numbers. The fixed-point signed multipliers operate on numbers represented in a fixed no. of fractional and integer bits, providing a more hardware-efficient solution for applications requiring deterministic precision. The inclusion of signed number support allows the handling of positive, negative values, making these multipliers suitable for a wide range of computations, including image processing, audio filtering, and machine learning algorithms [4]. Each convolution operation typically involves a series of multiplications and additions. High-speed multipliers on FPGA are designed to perform MAC operations as efficiently as possible, which directly impacts the speed of convolution operations. The implementation of multipliers with lesser delay and power supports faster convolution process. Multipliers in FPGA accelerators are designed to maximize performance, reduce power consumption and utilize hardware resources efficiently.

Combinational Path Delay (CPD) represents the time taken for a signal to travel through a longest combinational path, directly influencing the system's clock speed and performance. Techniques like optimized Booth encoding and strategic pipelining significantly contribute to CPD minimization by streamlining critical data paths. On the other hand, Energy Delay Product (EDP), which combines energy consumption and delay into a single metric, is reduced by incorporating power-saving techniques such as clock gating, reducing switching activity, and leveraging low-power FPGA primitives. Efficient resource utilization is a key consideration in FPGA-based design, particularly for computationally intensive components like multipliers. FPGAs offer limited programmable logic resources such as lookup tables (LUTs), flip-flops, DSP slices, and block RAMs, making their optimal use critical [3].

Techniques such as pipelining, resource sharing, and logic optimization ensure that these resources are utilized effectively without compromising performance. Thus implementing multipliers with optimized Booth encoding or partial product reduction techniques minimizes the need for additional logic resources. Techniques such as employing advanced Booth encoding methods, such as Booth Radix-4 or Radix-16, significantly decreases partial products that are generated, minimizing computation time. Additionally, efficient reduction, using 4:2 compressors involve in accelerating partial products addition. Pipeline optimization is the key methodology, introducing intermediate registers to balance combinational path delays and improve throughput.

Related Work

This work focuses to minimize the critical path delay (CPD) by employing Booth radix-4 partial product (PP) generation implemented with LUTs, combined with Bewick's sign extension and Dadda's concurrent PP reduction through a carry-save adder (CSA) for Xilinx (now AMD) FPGA devices. The proposed architecture effectively eliminates the dependency on an extended carry chain during PP reduction. In multipliers designed with Booth encoding (BE), the accurate PPs sign is established by the sign of the multiplicand and the corresponding BE value [1].

Field-programmable gate array (FPGA) vendors offer high-performance multipliers through dedicated DSP blocks. However, these DSP blocks have limitations, such as being fixed in number and location, leading to potential inefficiencies for smaller bit-width multiplications and introducing additional routing delays. To address these limitations, FPGA vendors also offer enhanced soft IP blocks for the multipliers. In the proposed multiplier design, the accurate implementation merges the creation and summation of two successive rows of partial product into a single stage, resulting in an efficient design [2].

When the pipeline stages are set beyond the optimal value, the core becomes fully pipelined, causing SRL16-based shift registers to be added at the output to accommodate the extra latency. The Vivado IDE performs thorough error-checking on all input parameters, providing resource estimation and optimal latency information to ensure efficient implementation [3].

The architectural differences between application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs) and FPGAs pose challenges to achieving the same performance gains in FPGA-based reconfigurable systems using ASIC-inspired approximation techniques. These differences underline the need for custom-designed multipliers tailored specifically for FPGA architectures to enhance their performance for reconfigurable computing applications [4].

The radix-4 Booth encoding/decoding method reduces the I/O count during the generation of PPs, enabling a single 6-input LUT that maps decoder and encoder. This approach effectively decreases the necessary rows by 50% relative to ripple-carry array multiplier. Additionally, the design avoids using a compressor tree, resulting in a simpler and more structured design that reduces slice resource usage by up to 50%. The design also supports multiply-accumulate (MAC) operations without requiring additional resources [5].

Designing and exploring various multipliers with adjustable approximation levels enable flexibility in balancing resource utilization, energy consumption, performance quality. This supports approximate computing at elevated abstraction tiers, making it possible to meet diverse application requirements. Such multiplier designs are synthesized using the Synopsys Design Compiler for a 45nm TSMC technology library and verified functionally through ModelSim gate-level simulations [6]. The radix-4 Booth encoding or decoding process using radix-4, in addition to reducing I/O requirements, allows Booth encoder and decoder to be implemented within a single LUT. This optimization approximately reduces the row count by half in contrast to ripple-carry multiplier while eliminating the need for a compressor tree. The resulting design offers an

efficient structure that utilizes significantly fewer resources, enabling support for multiply-accumulate (MAC) operations without extra hardware overhead [7].

To address the limitations of FPGA based DSP units, such as their predefined number, placement, and size of the bit constraints, improving soft logic- based multiplier implementations is crucial. This need has driven FPGA vendors to embed more efficient multiplier features into DSP blocks, reducing the disparity between ASICs and FPGAs for arithmetic-driven circuits [8].

In sample applications like image filtering and JPEG compression, the proposed architecture demonstrates superior performance, achieving 2x to 8x SNR for comparable power reduction when contrasted with voltage downscaling approaches. Enhancements like integrating a residual adder ensure correct multiplier operation for non-error-resilient designs [9].

Recent advancements in hardware accelerators, such as Nvidia GPUs equipped with tensor cores and Intel's AI-focused Stratix 10 NX FPGA, highlights trend toward specialized architectures for deep learning. Although peak performance metrics like 130 and 143 int8 TOPS are impressive, practical performance depends on achieving efficient real-world workload execution rather than relying solely on theoretical peak throughput [10].

Proposed Methodology

The fundamentals of the Booth's multiplication algorithm using radix-4 are used for designing the 4x4 multiplier block which uses less resources and introduces an area-efficient signed multiplier. Further low latency multiplier is designed by introducing the multiplexers for partial product selection and pipeline registers for optimization.

A. Partial Product Generation and Accumulation

The design of 4x4 multiplier focuses on optimizing both speed and area while maintaining computational accuracy. Partial products are generated and reduced efficiently to optimize computation. The reduction process minimizes the critical path delay. This ensures fast multiplication with reduced resource usage.

Booth radix-4 technique for PPG groups the bits into pairs and encodes them into fewer non-zero terms, significantly reducing the computational complexity. The 4x4 multiplier block considers 4 bits for input and produces 8-bit output employing Booth Radix-4 encoding for efficient partial product generation, reducing the number of required intermediate products. These partial products are combined with a 4:2 compressors for fast and efficient summation, following the Ripple Carry Adder (RCA) in producing final 8-bit output.

The partial product addition is carried out using 4:2 compressors combined with ripple carry adder (RCA) which involves combining multiple partial products generated during multiplication. The 4:2 compressors are used to reduce four input bits into two output bits (sum and carry), effectively minimizing the number of addition stages. These compressed results are then added together using a ripple carry adder, which sequentially propagates carries through the bits.

Fig. 1. Flow diagram of 4x4 multiplier design

The generation of partial products, accumulation along with multiplier design techniques are implemented as shown in Fig. 1. This reduction in rows the of partial products results in fewer addition operations, thereby shortening total delay of critical path and enhancing multiplier speed in the design. Bewick's Sign Extension (SE) approach is used in optimizing sign extension by reducing no. of bits needed for extending the sign in the binary number. Other than performing a simple replication of the sign bit, Bewick's technique efficiently extends the sign bit by using a combination of bitwise operations, reducing unnecessary logic and improving performance.

B. Optimizing Critical Path Delay

The implemented pipeline architecture plays a crucial role in enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of designed multipliers by minimizing critical path delay (CPD) and supporting high-speed operations. By dividing the multiplication process into sequential stages, the design effectively balances the computational load across clock cycles. This approach minimizes the propagation delay associated with processing complex operations in a single clock cycle, ensuring higher operating frequencies. The pipeline stages are optimized for signed fixed-point multiplication using Booth Radix-16 encoding, enabling efficient computation for both 16-bit and 32-bit multipliers.

The Radix-16 approach groups four bits at a time, significantly reducing the number of operations. This grouping leads to faster computation as fewer partial products are needed. A dedicated Multiplicand Sign Unit handles sign extension and encoding to ensure accurate signed multiplication, particularly for Booth Radix-16 operations. The Addition Unit is responsible for combining partial products efficiently, using optimized reduction techniques to minimize the critical path delay. Finally, the Shifting Unit aligns the partial products based on their positional significance, enabling accurate summation while reducing hardware complexity.

In the 16-bit multiplier, a two-stage pipeline architecture is implemented as shown in Fig. 2 to optimize the computation process. The 9x1 multiplexer is utilized in the Booth Radix-16 multiplier design to select appropriate multiplicand values based on the encoded Booth bits. It simplifies the partial product generation process by efficiently handling signed multiplicand values. This reduces logic complexity and enhances speed.

Fig. 2. Flow diagram for 16-bit & 32-bit multiplier implementation

The first pipeline stage is introduced after the addition and shifting operations for the final two rows of partial products, ensuring the intermediate results are efficiently processed before moving to the next step. This stage reduces the combinational delay by segmenting the addition and alignment process. The second pipeline stage is placed after generating the final summed output of 32 bits. This stage helps in stabilizing the output and prepares it for further processing or storage. By splitting the computational workload into two stages, the design minimizes the CPD, enabling faster and more reliable operation.

The 32-bit multiplier employs a three-stage pipeline architecture as given in Fig. 2, to handle the increased computational complexity effectively. In the first stage, four pipeline registers are introduced after an 8-bit shifting operation, ensuring the partial product rows are aligned and processed efficiently before moving to subsequent stages. The second stage includes two pipeline registers after a 16-bit shifting operation, further optimizing the alignment and addition of intermediate results.

Finally, the third pipeline stage is added after producing the final 64-bit output, stabilizing the computed product and preparing it for downstream operations. The signed fixed-point multiplication operations are effectively performed using these methodologies. These pipeline architectures enable efficient handling of partial product generation, addition, and shifting stages while ensuring high-speed operation with reduced critical path delay.

Results and Discussion

The evaluation of the designed multipliers, focuses on key performance metrics such as area, timing, and power. The results were analyzed on reducing the CPD and EDP. For the proposed work here, Verilog is utilized in the RTL implementation of various multiplier bit sizes. Xilinx Vivado 2023.1 is used for synthesizing and implementing the proposed multiplier designs on the Virtex-7 FPGA. Simulation and tools for analysis of power are employed to evaluate the consumption of the power.

Name	Slack ^{^1}	Levels	High Fanout	From	To	Total Delay	Logic Delay	Net Delay
Path 1	2.717	4	7	reg_in_b_reg[0]/C	topp_reg[7]/D	2.270	1.046	1.224
Path 2	2.747	4	7	reg_in_b_reg[0]/C	topp_reg[6]/D	2.240	1.016	1.224
Path 3	2.920	4	7	reg_in_b_reg[0]/C	topp_reg[5]/D	2.067	0.843	1.224

Fig. 3. Timing analysis of 4-bit multiplier

The timing report analysis provides the Combinational Path Delay of the multiplier design. The Fig. 3 describes timing report indicates that the total delay for the 4-bit multiplier design is 2.270 ns.

Name	Slack ^{^1}	Levels	High Fan...	From	To	Total Delay	Logic Delay	Net Delay
Path 1	3.305	5	1	pipe_re...[13]/C	pipe_s...[31]/D	1.672	0.805	0.867
Path 2	3.358	4	1	pipe_re...[13]/C	pipe_s...[21]/D	1.619	0.752	0.867
Path 3	3.360	5	1	pipe_re...[13]/C	pipe_s...[24]/D	1.617	0.750	0.867

Fig. 4. Timing analysis of 16-bit multiplier

The timing analysis of the 16-bit multiplier design in Fig. 4 shows a reduced Critical Path Delay of 1.672 ns.

Name	Slack ^{^1}	Levels	High Fanout	From	To	Total Delay	Logic Delay	Net Delay
Path 1	1.803	10	15	pipe2_reg2_reg[18]/C	pipe_sum...lca_5/D	2.848	1.041	1.807
Path 2	1.914	10	15	pipe2_reg2_reg[18]/C	pipe_sum...lca_3/D	2.727	1.041	1.686
Path 3	1.921	10	15	pipe2_reg2_reg[18]/C	pipe_sum...lca_4/D	2.738	1.041	1.697

Fig. 5. Timing analysis of 32-bit multiplier

The timing report for the 32-bit multiplier in Fig. 5 indicates a total delay of 2.848 ns, which is relatively low, highlighting the efficiency of the design. A reduced CPD, observed in the report, indicates an efficient pipeline and logic optimization. This analysis ensures the multiplier design meets the desired timing constraints for high-speed FPGA applications.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF THE PROPOSED MULTIPLIERS

DESIGN	4x4			16x16			32x32		
	LUTs	CPD[ns]	EDP[zJs]	LUTs	CPD[ns]	EDP[zJs]	LUTs	CPD[ns]	EDP[zJs]
Proposed	18	2.270	18.3	288	1.672	345.1	1646	2.848	1187.6
Radix-4 [1]	23	1.775	3.15	270	3.965	125.72	1054	5.379	868
BE [4]	22	3.34	4.57	296	7.33	93.16	1121	9.65	354.33
Vivado IP [3]	18	2.14	2.27	286	4.27	146.62	1103	5.81	861.45
Softcore Multiplier [7]	24	3.84	9.55	217	9.52	313.56	700	16.25	1631.7
Approximate Multiplier [6]	18	2.23	2.25	404	7.03	156.87	1512	9.57	322.10

Table I provides a detailed comparison of consumption of resources (LUTs), combinational path delay (CPD), and energy- delay product (EDP) for the multiplier that is proposed alongside several state-of-the-art approximate and the accurate multiplier designs. The results in table I reflect the performance of "Radix-4 [1]," "BE [4]," "Vivado IP [3]," "Softcore Multiplier [7]," and "Approximate Multiplier [6]" multipliers. These include the additional overhead introduced by signed-unsigned converters, ensuring a fair evaluation of the designs under similar conditions. The proposed multiplier consistently achieves superior performance in CPD, with minimal LUT usage for 4x4 multiplier, highlighting its efficiency and practical applicability in resource-constrained FPGA-based systems.

The area utilization report provides insights into the FPGA resources consumed by each multiplier, including LUTs, flip-flops, and DSP slices. The timing report analysis provides the Combinational Path Delay (CPD) of the multiplier design, which represents the total delay from the longest combinational path in the circuit. This delay is a combination of both the net delay and the logic delay. The power report generated from Vivado provides detailed insights into the power consumption of the designed multipliers. It includes static and dynamic power.

The proposed multiplier demonstrates notable advantages in performance across 4x4, 16x16, and 32x32 configurations, particularly excelling in reducing critical path delay (CPD). For the 4x4 multiplier, the proposed design uses only 18 LUTs, achieving the minimum area usage among all compared designs. This low resource consumption highlights the efficiency of the design for smaller bit-widths.

The compact nature of the 4-bit multiplier makes it well-suited for applications where area constraints are critical. In the 16x16 configuration, the proposed multiplier achieves the lowest CPD of 1.672 ns, a significant improvement over other designs. This represents a reduction of 57.83% in delay compared to Radix-4 [1], underscoring the impact of the advanced partial product generation and reduction techniques. Similarly, it outperforms the BE multiplier [4] with a 62.16% reduction in delay, highlighting its optimized design for balancing area and performance.

Fig. 6. Comparison of proposed 4x4 signed multiplier with other multipliers

From the Fig. 6 it can be seen that the 4-bit multiplier design consumes less number of hardware resources.

Fig. 7. Comparison of proposed 16x16 signed multiplier with other multipliers

From Fig. 7 it can be observed that 16-bit multiplier has reduced delay compared to other multipliers.

Fig. 8. Comparison of proposed 32x32 signed multiplier with other multipliers

The design of 32-bit proposed multiplier with lesser delay can be seen from Fig. 8 which can be used in high- speed fpga based applications. The signed number multiplication operation is implemented to handle both positive and negative inputs efficiently. A performance comparison table for the multipliers highlights key metrics such as area utilization (LUTs), timing (CPD), and power consumption (EDP) across different bit-widths. Inferring from the table I the 4- bit multiplier achieves minimal area usage with only 18 LUTs, showcasing its compact design. Meanwhile, the 16- bit and 32-bit multipliers exhibit significantly reduced delays, with the 16-bit multiplier having delay of 1.672 ns and 32-bit multiplier achieving a total delay of 2.848 ns, reflecting the effectiveness of the pipeline and optimization techniques in enhancing speed.

Conclusion

This work contributes to the advancement of FPGA- based architectures by providing scalable and optimized solutions for multiplication operations, a cornerstone of many complex algorithms. Booth radix-16 encoding, pipeline optimization, and efficient partial product reduction techniques were employed to achieve the significant improvements in performance and resource utilization. Timing analysis confirmed reduced delay for 16-bit and 32-bit multipliers, while power reports validated the energy efficiency of the designs. The 4-bit multiplier demonstrated minimal area consumed. The potential for achieving an optimal balance between computational speed and hardware efficiency is carried out, making it suitable for modern digital signal processing applications.

The future scope lies in further optimizing the multiplier design for even lower power consumption while maintaining high speed and area efficiency. Extending the multiplier design to support a broader range of high-performance computing tasks, like machine learning, processing of signals and image processing.

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